

Motionless balls in a body of revolution

Harald Schröer

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1 The frictionless case:

We want to occupy ourselves with the balance of two balls on a spherical shell. We have the following questions: Is this balance stable, unstable, or indifferent? What position do the two balls have? Which quantities determine the balance?

Two balls with mass m_1, m_2 and radii R_1, R_2 are on a body of revolution shell with the radius R_K .

We don't take friction into consideration. At first, we assume a vacuum.

Then the force on an inclined plane with the angle of inclination β is:

$$F = mg \sin \beta$$

see fig.

m =moved mass g =earth's acceleration

On the shell the forces are:

$$F_i = m_i g \sin \gamma_i \quad i = 1, 2$$

with: $h(r)$ = revolution body's function

$s = h'(r)$

R_1, R_2 = radii of the balls

m_1, m_2 = mass of the balls

Two balls lie on the shell of a body of revolution

cosine law:

$$c^2 = a^2 + b^2 - 2ab \cos \gamma \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \cos \gamma = \frac{a^2 + b^2 - c^2}{2ab}$$

With the figure, we recognize:

$$a^2 = (h_2 + R_2 \cos \gamma_2)^2 + (r_2 - R_2 \sin \gamma_2)^2$$

$$b^2 = (h_1 + R_1 \cos \gamma_1)^2 + (r_1 - R_1 \sin \gamma_1)^2$$

$$c = R_1 + R_2$$

Positions of the midpoints (x_1, y_1) and (x_2, y_2) :

$$x_1 = r_1 - R_1 \sin \gamma_1 \quad x_2 = r_2 - R_2 \sin \gamma_2$$

$$y_1 = h_1 + R_1 \cos \gamma_1 \quad y_2 = h_2 + R_2 \cos \gamma_2$$

(r_1, h_1) and (r_2, h_2) are the coordinates of the touching points between ball and body of revolution.

$$h_1 = h(r_1) \quad h_2 = h(r_2) \quad s_1 = h'(r_1) \quad s_2 = h'(r_2)$$

γ_1, γ_2 are pitch angles, as well, see figure.

it is valid:

$$s_1 = \tan \alpha_1 \quad s_2 = \tan \alpha_2$$

$$\sin \alpha = \frac{\tan \alpha}{\sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha}} \quad \cos \alpha = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha}}$$

it follows:

$$\sin \gamma_1 = \frac{s_1}{\sqrt{1 + s_1^2}} \quad \sin \gamma_2 = \frac{s_2}{\sqrt{1 + s_2^2}}$$

$$\cos \gamma_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + s_1^2}} \quad \cos \gamma_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + s_2^2}}$$

With the following figure we recognize one equation:

$$\gamma = \arctan \frac{x_1}{y_1} + \arctan \frac{x_2}{y_2}$$

Falling force components:

$$F_1 = m_1 g \sin \gamma_1 \quad F_2 = m_2 g \sin \gamma_2$$

see figure:

It must be $F_1 = F_2$.

$$\Rightarrow m_1 g \cdot \frac{s_1}{\sqrt{1+s_1^2}} = m_2 g \cdot \frac{s_2}{\sqrt{1+s_2^2}}$$

We yield 2 equations:

$$\frac{m_1 s_1}{\sqrt{1+s_1^2}} = \frac{m_2 s_2}{\sqrt{1+s_2^2}} \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma = \arctan \frac{x_1}{y_1} + \arctan \frac{x_2}{y_2} \quad (2)$$

The equations of $\gamma, x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2$ must be inserted in equation (2). Then the equations (1) and (2) are 2 equations of the unknowns r_1, r_2 .

We note that the unknowns r_1, r_2 are in the equations of $\cos \gamma$, and that $\sin \gamma_1, \sin \gamma_2, \cos \gamma_1, \cos \gamma_2$ must be inserted, as well. Solving r_1 and r_2 is complicated.

In a medium the forces only change to:

$$F_1 = m_1 a_1 g \cdot \frac{s_1}{\sqrt{1+s_1^2}} \quad F_2 = m_2 a_2 g \cdot \frac{s_2}{\sqrt{1+s_2^2}}$$

with $a_1 = 1 - \frac{\varphi_F}{\varphi_{K1}}$, $a_2 = 1 - \frac{\varphi_F}{\varphi_{K2}}$

φ_F = density of the medium (liquid, gas)

φ_{K1} = density of the first ball

φ_{K2} = density of the second ball

see Budo [2] §16 p.85

Equation (1) changes to:

$$\frac{m_1 a_1 s_1}{\sqrt{1+s_1^2}} = \frac{m_2 a_2 s_2}{\sqrt{1+s_2^2}}$$

Equation (2) is the same.

$h(r)$ must be so, that the two balls have only **one** touching point.

Thus no throughs, where a ball settles down.

If we insert for $h(r)$ the equations of an ellipse, parabola, hyperbola, or cone, we get the equations of revolution ellipsoid shells, revolution parabola shells, revolution hyperbola shells, and revolution cone shells.

We assume that the densities of both balls are greater than the density of the medium. If we have the reverse case, than the body of revolution must be turned round. see fig.

This inversion is valid to the friction case, as well (section 2). Instead of the revolution body shell, we can view a lateral area of a general cylinder with the form of a revolution body. see fig.

Then we have the same equations of motionless revolution bodies of the same type, thus the same moment of inertia. This is valid to the later treated friction case, as well.

In the case of a spherical shell, it is a circular cylinder. In the case of a parabola shell, it is a parabola cylinder.

In the frictionless case, both balls have a stable balance.

2 Motionless balls on the shell with friction

Now we view the friction case. We will see that there is a free play because of the friction forces - in contrast to the frictionless case.

The notation is the same as in section 1.

$m_1, m_2 =$ mass of the balls
 $R_1, R_2 =$ radii of the balls
 $R_K =$ radius of the spherical shell

In the friction case, there is free play because of friction forces F_{R1} and F_{R2} .

$F_{R1}, F_{R2} =$ friction case of the balls with the radii R_1 and R_2 .

Here γ_1, γ_2 are pitch angles of the balls as in section 1. The forces can be written as:

$$F_1 = \delta_1 m_1 g \sin \gamma_1 \quad F_2 = \delta_2 m_2 g \sin \gamma_2 \quad (3)$$

$$F_{R1} = m_1 g \cos \gamma_1 \cdot \mu_1 \quad F_{R2} = m_2 g \cos \gamma_2 \cdot \mu_2$$

with $i \in \{1, 2\}$

$$\delta_i := \begin{cases} \frac{5}{7} & \text{if } \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} < \mu_{Hi} \text{ (rolling)} \\ 1 & \text{if } \mu_{Hi} < \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} \text{ (sliding)} \\ \frac{5}{7} \text{ or } 1 & \text{if } \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} = \mu_{Hi} \neq 0 \text{ (decision remains open)} \\ 1 & \text{if } 0 = \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} = \mu_{Hi} \text{ (frictionless)} \end{cases}$$

see Assmann [1] edition 1 chapter 11.10 p. 265

μ'_i = rolling friction coefficient of the ball i with radius R_i

μ_{Hi} = static friction coefficient of the ball i

μ_{Gi} = sliding friction coefficient of the ball i

and

$$\mu_i = \begin{cases} \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} & \text{if } \mu_{Hi} > \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} \text{ (rolling)} \\ \mu_{Gi} & \text{if } \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} > \mu_{Hi} \text{ (sliding)} \\ \mu_{Gi} \text{ or } \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} & \text{if } \mu_{Hi} = \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} \text{ (decision remains open)} \end{cases}$$

see Assmann [1] edition 1 chapter 11.10 p.265

The acceleration b on the inclined plane is:

$$b = \delta g \cdot \sin \alpha, \text{ the velocity } v \text{ and the distance } s \text{ are } v = \delta g \sin \alpha \cdot t \text{ and } s = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \delta g \cdot t^2 \cdot \sin \alpha.$$

If a ball is rolling on the inclined plane, it is $\delta = \frac{5}{7}$ i.e. Budo [2] §57 p.302 Gl. (8). The moment of inertia J of a ball is $J = \frac{2}{5} \cdot mR^2$. The general formula for rolling on the inclined plane can be written:

$$b = \frac{mg \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{J}{R^2}} \quad (4)$$

One derivation can be found at * at the end of the chapter or we can see this with Budo [2] §57 p.302 Gl. (5)-(7). The ball's moment of inertia insertion leads to:

$$b = \frac{mg \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{2}{5} \cdot m} = \frac{5}{7} \cdot g \sin \alpha \quad (5)$$

Then we have, in the case of rolling, $\delta = \frac{5}{7}$.

The notations are the same as in section 1.

$h(r)$ = revolution body function

$s = h'(r)$

R_1, R_2 = radii of the balls

m_1, m_2 = mass of the balls

We make the same assumptions about the revolution body function $h(r)$ as in the frictionless case in section 1.

It is valid for $i \in \{1, 2\}$:

$$F_i = \delta_i m_i g \sin \gamma_i \quad F_{Ri} = m_i g \cos \gamma_i \cdot \mu_i$$

We know from section 1:

$$\sin \gamma_i = \frac{s_i}{\sqrt{1 + s_i^2}} \quad \cos \gamma_i = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + s_i^2}}$$

with

$$s_i = h'(r_i)$$

It follows:

$$F_i = \frac{m_i g s_i \cdot \delta_i}{\sqrt{1 + s_i^2}} \quad F_R = \frac{m_i g \cdot \mu_i}{\sqrt{1 + s_i^2}}$$

Stability inequality: $|\cdot| = \text{value in } R$

$$|F_1 - F_2| \leq F_{R1} + F_{R2}$$

limit cases:

$$F_1 - F_2 = F_{R1} + F_{R2}$$

$$F_2 - F_1 = F_{R1} + F_{R2}$$

Both of these equations must be used instead of (1) from section 1. All the other equations are the same as in the frictionless case in section 1. The unknowns r_1, r_2 are searched for these equations. Because of the stability inequality we get subintervals of r_1, r_2 .

In a medium (liquid, gas) the forces have the factors $a_1 = 1 - \frac{\varphi F}{\varphi_{K1}}$ and $a_2 =$

$1 - \frac{\varphi_F}{\varphi_{K2}}$ see Budo [2] §16 p.85. φ_F is the density of the liquid and $\varphi_{K1}, \varphi_{K2}$ are the densities of both balls. Then we obtain the forces:

$$F_i = \frac{m_i g s_i a_i \cdot \delta_i}{\sqrt{1 + s_i^2}}$$

$$F_{Ri} = \frac{m_i g a_i \cdot \mu_i}{\sqrt{1 + s_i^2}}$$

All the other equations remain unchanged.

We get the equations of revolution conic sections (ellipsoid, paraboloid, hyperboloid, cone) if we insert for $h(r)$ the equation of an ellipse, parabola, hyperbola, or cone.

Both balls are in stable balance in a determined area. If we move the balls out of the area, then the balls move to their previous position. However, in this determined area, both balls can be shifted arbitrary. That means an indifferent balance in this determined area.

to *: The derivation of formula (4):

Notations:

kinetic energy = $E_{kin} = \frac{mv^2}{2}$

potential energy = $E_{pot} = mgh$ with $h = h_s \sin \alpha$ see fig.

rotational energy = $E_{rot} = \frac{Jw^2}{2}$ $J =$ moment of inertia

law of conservation of energy:

$$\frac{mv^2}{2} + \frac{Jw^2}{2} = mgh$$

We assume that the body is only rolling not sliding. Then it is valid:

angular velocity = $w = \frac{v}{R}$ $R =$ radius of the rolling body

$$\frac{mv^2}{2} + \frac{Jv^2}{2R^2} = mgh_s \sin \alpha$$

With transformation we yield:

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{2mgh_s \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{J}{R^2}}}$$

Because the rolling body has the constant acceleration $b = g \sin \alpha$, there is a uniform accelerated motion. For this motion it is valid: $v^2 = 2h_s \cdot b$ transformed to $b = \frac{v^2}{2h_s}$. Now we insert the equation of v :

$$b = \frac{2mgh_s \sin \alpha}{2h_s \cdot \left(m + \frac{J}{R^2}\right)} = \frac{mg \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{J}{R^2}}$$

Then we have the wanted formula.

References

- [1] Bruno Assmann "Technische Mechanik" volume 1 Oldenbourg Verlag 12.edition Munich 1991
- [2] A Budo "Theoretische Mechanik" 10.edition VEB Deutscher Verlag der Wissenschaften Berlin 1980